

AVATARS AS MOTIVATIONAL FACTOR IN SIMULATION GAMES

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Abstract: *User motivation and engagement while playing serious games remains challenging. Advances location-based technology has brought new opportunities for game-based, context-regulated experiences. Much effort has been made to model and manage the user context data, devices, and pervasive spaces, in order to enhance user experience. Research indicates that avatars have potential beyond representing the player on screen and interacting with the digital world. The interaction between an avatar and a player contributes to higher user engagement and a more pervasive experience. This article will look at how Simulation Games used for educational purposes can profit from avatars. The article is outlined as followed: it first analyses the potential avatars have on increasing player motivation and game enjoyment as well as on the player behaviour within different game genres. In a second step, we analyse and identify different types of simulation games, which mostly do not integrate an avatar. Based upon the outcome of the first part, we transfer the gained knowledge about avatars in avatar-focused games to simulation-based games with an educational focus on engineering, in order to increase player engagement towards learning games.*

Keywords: *serious game; simulation; engineering; avatar; engagement; intrinsic motivation.*

I. Introduction

The usage of simulations and simulation based educational games (often also classified as business or management games) as an integral part of the engineering education has, despite still a quite low penetration rate, a long tradition within German engineering education [1]. Games are often used as a tool to overcome the gap between theory and practice [2]. Simulation games are the most used type within engineering and managerial education. [1]. With simulation games, we understand a series of instructional designs using elements from simulation and gaming [2]. Such games “allow participants to experience and explore a simulated problem in a practical and pragmatic manner” [3]. These games can be both digital and non-digital and can be seen as a sub-class of serious games.

The advantage of using simulation games in an educational context is that it can enable learners to cope with real problems and authentic situations in a safe environment [4][5]. In engineering and management education, simulations are often scenario-based or case-based. Here, events of the real world are often used as a means to elicit critical decision-making. As such, simulations have attempted to mirror the real world [6]. Semini et al. [2006 in [1]] state that games are more suitable than simulations to teach decision-making in Supply Chains, due to the explorative environment. Digitalised simulation games are generally case-based computer models, which are used with the objective to answer effectively the issue raised by the case such as the optimization of profits, costs or lead times. The player can choose among a tremendous realm of policies, try them out; and get the interactive feedback. During this process of trial and error, users are supposed to acquire experiential learning [1]. However, due to the close link to the reality and the usage of real world processes, many simulation games are less focusing on motivation and engagement, which are two very important factors for the learning outcome [7]. The main research questions are therefore how to get such games more immersive, without increasing the complexity, as well as to identify what we can learn from entertainment games. These are well-known for their ability to engage and motivate and to let the person feel immersed within the gaming environment. A literature review as well as a questionnaire (N~500) indicated that the use of avatars contributed to an immersed feeling of the players. The main objective of this article is therefore firstly to analyse how avatars have been implemented as well as

their benefits in different genres, for different objectives etc. before investigating how this can be transferred to simulation games for increasing the engagement and immersiveness. A secondary objective was to test the concept derived from the analysis in an existing game. The test game used is a simulation game used for strategic decision making, target group master students.

II. Methodology

The focus of the article is on investigating an avatar's contribution to engagement and motivation in multi-player simulation games for students in secondary and higher education. The methodological approach is a mixed- methods approach: Two unstructured literature reviews were carried out using google scholar: In the first, carried out in 2014-2015 the main focus was on avatars and exergames (Games combined with physical exercises) (key words used were related to avatars, motivation, impact, effect, serious games and exergames). The output of this unstructured approach was limited, so in addition to reading the full papers accessed through google scholar, also articles cited in these were analysed. A second review still using google scholar was carried out in January 2017. The focus was now more on simulation game and avatar; Key words used gamification, simulation game, avatar, use of avatar simulation games; "effect of avatar" serious games engineering [8]. The relevance of the downloaded papers was based on assessing the abstract, as well as by searching for the combination of avatar and motivation in the full papers. The second part of the research has a different methodical approach. The authors are involved in the research related to specifications and development of serious games, what serious game design can learn from entertainment games as well as avatar design, so Design Science was the overall scientific approach in this work [8][9][10], more specific, action research was applied [11].

III. State of the Art

Recent research addresses the effect and potentials of avatars in video games. This chapter summarises the different views/findings. Within serious gaming, avatars are used with good results for Exergames. In other genres, like simulation games for educational purposes, there is hardly any research on the usage of avatars. Consequently, the state of the art provides an overview about the beneficial usage of avatars in various entertainment games as well as Exergames.

At the beginning, an avatar represented a player on screen [12]. Through this representation, the user can interact with the virtual environment, explore the digital world and perceive reward and punishment. "Therefore users/players have an attachment to them, an investment in them" [12]. According to Gazzard, this connectedness is essential in the definition of an avatar, as this separates it from the other game objects in the virtual world [12]. More recent research indicates however, that the avatar is much more than a representation on screen. Looking at how avatars influence the players shows effect. In two studies it is analysed how avatars in exergames influence motion. In [13] the results indicate that a thin avatar's body shape had higher influence on the game task (motion) than that of an obese player representation. These results were confirmed by [14]. There are also several studies related to avatars and game enjoyment, intrinsic motivation as well as identification in non-motion-based games. In games in which a player representation is the/a key for the game play, it is often possible to create their character on their own and try out different identities and roles using an avatar editor [15]. Trepte, Reinecke, & Behr [16] found that the creation of an avatar strongly depends on the game genre. [16] identified that for competitive games, the players create avatars matching the game requirements more than their own identity, whereas it is the opposite for non-competitive games. This representation of the player's real ego increases the identification to her/his avatar, which has a positive influence on engagement and game enjoyment [16],[17].The identification especially increases the more emotions the player develops to it [18]. This means, the more variables a player can personalise in the avatar editor, the more emotionally attached the player feels [18], inducing increased

intrinsic motivation [19]. Consequently, it will make a large difference in which in-game avatar editor a player can use. A comparison of three different editors currently available on the market (“Sims 3”, Wii and Xbox 360 console) shows the different opportunities.

“The Sims 3” avatar editor focuses on the creation of realistic looking digital persons. Therefore, it offers a broad range of options (i.e. seamless adjustable shape of head and body, but also incremental details on several objects like upper lid, shape of eyes, rotation etc.). Regarding colours, the editor can select from the whole RGB palette for several parts of the body and the head (e.g. skin, hair, eyebrows, etc.). However, since freely selectable, it also provides the player with a lot of freedom in his creativity and personalisation of an avatar. The level of granularity possible in the avatar editors offered by the Wii and the Xbox 360 is much lower. The focus is here more on avatars of comic style, more related to expression than to realism, but recognition is possible as they work with drawn facial attributes for mouth and eyes. While the shape of the bodies of the Xbox 360 editor avatars are based on real human proportions, Miis (avatars of the Wii), employ simple geometric shapes [20] and with less colours than Sims 3. However, in contrast to the Xbox 360’s editor the one of the Wii offers the opportunity to move, scale and rotate all facial attributes and accessories (glasses, rings, etc.). [21] states that using player-customised avatars intensifies the game experience so that players in a collaborative game mode were more willing to help (outside the gameplay) than players in a competitive one, and that this effect was even more recognisable for players using own customized avatars compared with participants using a generic gender-appropriate avatar [21]. This is in-line with Social Cognitive Theory [22][23] which claims that “humans can learn behaviours through the observation of [role] models [22][23]” [24]. Applied on avatars it implies that a strong identification with the avatar, may lead to feeling that an avatar’s attributes were their own [25]. A study of Fox & Bailenson shows that users may adapt their behaviour accordingly [24]. Also outside a game context, avatars may play a significant role. [26] found out that a digital avatar can help students to overcome the barrier to stand up and speak. This study states that student would not have been able to present some topics, because of being frightened of the possible reactions of their mates. Furthermore, a study showing that the motivation and interest was increased by gamifying an engineering course, also revealed that the interviewed students would have preferred to have an avatar as a virtual representation in the environment to gain reputation and to get involved [27]. Even though the research shows that avatars affect player’s behaviour, motivation and enjoyment, it is still not much known about the potential and limits in using avatars in the type of games mostly used for engineering education- simulation based games based on real world processes. This article tries to bring that research on step forward.

IV. Research Approach and results of pre-studies

The previous section describes which positive effects avatars, specifically personalised avatars may have on the players’ motivation and engagement. At the same time many educational games are criticised for not being engaging and motivating and put too little attention into the enjoyment of playing games [1]. Due to the huge potential avatars have, we ask, can we use the positive effects of avatars in simulation-based learning games in the engineering context? There are many different types of simulation games on the market and most of them do not contain a representation of the player. Life simulations such as “The Sims”, are designed in a way that the player controls multiple digital humans in their everyday life. The player her/himself is not represented in the game, since her/his role is more of a god. The player controls and manages most of the digital universe and its residents in a bird’s eye perspective and does not appear in the game. The player can neither interact with the virtual humans, (s)he rather lets those interact with each other or other objects. This is also true for games like “Rollercoaster Tycoon” and “Sim City”, which focus even more on processes. There are also games which simulate the steering of a craft, such as an airplane or train in which it seems that an avatar plays no important role. Usually, those simulations are played in the first person perspective to fully immerse the player in her/his role in the cockpit. The third-person view is then used to observe the vehicle from several perspectives. The focus in these games is fully on the vehicle and its

functionalities. Simulation games in the field of learning in engineering often reproduce processes, e.g. logistics, risk management or process chains. Also in these games, the player is more in a controlling position like in “The Sims” or “Sims City” and often there is no specific need for the game process to display the player on screen. Our research question is therefore if the integration of a player-representing avatar in a learning simulation-game for engineering students will have an impact on player motivation and enjoyment. As a part of an analysis for a research project on pervasive games, we have collected feedback on users’ preferences regarding game genre. An analysis of n= 276 questionnaires (N=495, only 276 could be used for this specific question), delivered by French students, mostly between 15 and 20 years, revealed that when they were asked to name their three favourite games of all times, gave a list of 202 games of diverse genres and platforms. About 2/3 of participants’ favourite games include an avatar. About 26% mentioned games were of the genre “role playing game” (RPG). A key function here is to improve the avatar’s skills and equipment to progress in the game. Another 11% mentioned life simulation games, such as The Sims or Tomodachi Life, in which avatars play an elemental role. Here, they do not represent the player her/himself but the player controls them and often identifies with them and therefore they are a vital part for the game play. Another example would be the FIFA series. FIFA is the most frequently named game in our study (24%). Also in this game, the player is not embodied by one figure in the game, but (s)he has the control over multiple avatars. The selection of who will play on the field strongly depends on factors such as, sympathy to the person in the real world and skills. Only three of the 10 best rated games do not focus on the avatar of the player. One of them does not contain a player representation at all (“Candy Crush Saga”). The other two are first-person-shooters, which do represent the player in the game, but rather want to immerse the player in his role and the game than interrupting this with the display of an avatar. The focus of the other 7 favourite games lies on the avatar itself. It is the main part the games are about. For instance, the avatar can level up, develop skills and change clothes and armour. Based on the analysis as well as the findings reported in the state of the art, we assume that an avatar will have a positive effect and plays an important role for engagement and game enjoyment, and therefore can be used as game mechanism for increasing the engagement in simulation based games used in educational context.

In order to test this hypothesis, we analysed different games we have been using for several years in different educational context. One game, Seconds, used in our education of post-graduate engineering students, is a multi-player simulation based game for strategic decision making in production networks. It was designed for 20-50 players. The game evolves as the players interact. A company can be played by 1- 3 players, and the aim is to produce different products and evolving the business on long term. The game starts with an initial company strategy and a short company description. The game has several key performance indicators (KPIs) allowing the players to see the progress and the status which is used both for benchmarking as well as target in game play [7]. Used in the context it is designed for, the evaluation results are positive regarding motivation and engagement, but for smaller classes we have observed, that the engaging factor is dropping due to too little interaction. However, increasing the complexity to get more interaction, leads to overloading the students, i.e. they get stressed. During the last two years we have therefore been looking into how to keep the engagement also for smaller groups. The interesting aspect of using this game as a test bed is that the learning outcome is rated quite high [7], and that there is difference in user engagement depending on interaction. The main focus is on decision making and its effects on different stakeholders, very different from simulation games within entertainment like “Sim City” or “Rollercoaster Tycoon”. In order to test the hypothesis, we created a concept for the integration of an avatar, representing the player. The feedback from the players were collected using questionnaires. The students involved in the game play were the course participants. In order to measure the effect of our conceptual integration of an avatar into game play the same questionnaire was completed twice- first after playing a session of ca. 3 h, then the concept was introduced and explained and the students were asked to complete the questionnaire again. The questionnaire was designed for collecting user experience related overall game play experience in terms of enjoyment, competence, effort, tension, choice and social

interaction. It uses the social presence scale of the “Game Experience Questionnaire” (GEQ; 17 items) [28] and the “Intrinsic Motivation Inventory” (IMI; 21 items) [29]. The next section reports of the findings from this first experiment.

V. Effects of Avatars

This section first describes the concept developed for avatar integration before it presents the results of the small scale experiment.

Concept of Avatar Integration

The main learning objective in the course in which we use “Seconds” is related to decision-making in distributed production network. As described above, the narrative develops with the play time and is driven by the interaction between the players. The goal is to successfully run and develop the company by producing different components and products in co-operation with other players. The GUIs are quite static, since it is a set of different overviews related to typical KPIs for a company and its production. The GUIs comprise all information a player need to monitor, control and operate his company, but the GUI is rather complex and requires quite some time for getting used to it. The complexity is high, and requires that the player knows what to look for terms of KPIs related to different decisions (see Figure 1). A representation of the player within the game is not necessary for fulfilling the given tasks. Nevertheless, the player her/himself plays an important role, as (s)he interacts with other existing players. This differentiates this type of game from games, mentioned above, where the player manages and controls the entire game world. However, the game focuses on communication and collaboration, and therefore, we expect that offering a customisable avatar for each role/player would support the identification with the role in the game play.

Figure 1 Selection of Seconds user interfaces

According to Misoch this process should lead to a higher emotional attachment and therefore to an increased intrinsic motivation, in contrast to just selecting a predefined avatar [18]. The implementation foresees that, before starting the game play at the very beginning, each student would customize their own avatar’s head, using an integrated avatar editor, which would work similar to the free online tool on “avatarmaker.com”. The avatars are displayed in a comic style. The user can choose the gender, haircut, shape of eyes, nose, mouth, ears and eyebrows and the colour for each part. The size and angle can be adjusted as well as the style and colour of the shirt.

This avatar then represents the player in Seconds (Figure 2). Using the avatar, the player will be able to express her/his feelings and mood, which we consider to be motivating as the player can interact with her/his representation as well as with their co-players even better. The user can select the avatar’s mood, choosing one of 4 different images. The avatar can be smiling, have a neutral, severe and enraged face. This picture will be displayed next to the name in the group chat. Everyone can see how the player is feeling and has the chance to respond to this mood in their messages. The idea is that the mood of the

Figure 2 Seconds avatar concept

avatar will represent the mood of the player and be used in private emails and contract negotiations and be set apart from the overall status.

If the user is happy about an offer (s)he can select the smiling face in her respond. If (s)he is not satisfied or even angry this can be communicated to the co-player at once by selecting the right mood of the avatar. This will allow the player to react individually to every single thread in a more natural manner than having to express it in words. According to the theory, the relationships in the game would be felt more intense

and might immerse the player more into her/his role in the game.

Results of Questionnaires

As described, we used a questionnaire to detect the differences in the social presence and intrinsic motivation of players between the current game and the game with the new avatar concept. 12 post-graduate students participated and the tests were conducted as described above. For the IMI, we used a Likert Scale with 5 values. Figure 3 shows that the students have moderate interest and enjoyment in

Figure 3 Results of test of Avatar concept of Seconds

the basic game. As can be seen in Figure 3, the enjoyment of the participants slightly increased with the new concept. This also holds for the answers on perceived competence and effort/importance. Also, the pressure/tension increased a bit, while the perceived choice minimally decreased. However, these differences are minor and since the highest value is a difference of 0.2, the results are not significant. The same is true for the social presence questionnaire, which consists of 3 questions, again using the same Likert scale. Due to the effect avatars can have to intensify the players' feelings [21], we expected the psychological involvement to increase. However, again the results indicate that the effect is measureable, but minor both for positive and in the negative feelings. The behavioural involvement is indifferent. The conclusion of the small experiment is therefore, that the conditions for the positive effects of avatars on motivation and engagement are depending on more factors than we thought.

VI. Discussion

The hypothesis, that players in an ok, daengineering simulation game will become more engaged by the integration of an avatar remains unconfirmed, even though not excluded. There might be several reasons for this, so that we have to analyse the details and repeat the experiment in order to

understand the limitation and pre-requisites better, but then with a mock-up and simple implementation and not only by assessing a concept. The lack of real interaction might have led to less attachment and identification with their avatar, which is an essential factor for the growth of the intrinsic motivation. Another consideration is that the type of simulation game was the wrong choice, since there are several types of simulation games used for engineering education. In our experiment, we used a game for strategic decision making, in which the personal appearance plays a minor role. The communication between the players works as realistic as it would be in the real world through emails and chats, thus less need of an avatar for communication. However, the students referred to in [27] remarked that they would have liked an avatar representing them in forums and highscore lists. The class management software described in [27] (see chapter 2) has a similar view as the dashboard view of the game “Seconds”: the user sees documents, chats and emails. Based on that, we expected that that also would hold for Seconds, which could not be fully confirmed in our small experiment. A further reason might be that the game requires the players to follow all KPIs and analyse what happens. This leads to a high working load (the reason why we could not increase the complexity), so that they do not spend time on activities they know have little impact on the KPIs (like setting the mood of the avatar when communicating with their classmates), or they do not feel like it when stressed. We therefore want to repeat the experiment with a different game, also a role based multi-user game, used in the same course. But here, the game play is more on operational level, less on strategical like in Seconds. For the learning outcome, as well as for the engagement during gameplay, we know that how immersed the students feel, is essential [1] for keeping them in flow during the game and also to reduce the stress level. Here a representation is more similar to what we have seen in exergames, and thus we would like to see if the results of adding an avatar here will have similar positive effects like reported on in entertainment games.

VII. Conclusion & Future Work

In this article, we described the importance of avatars in video games. A study among French pupils (N ~500, of which n=276 could be used for this article. The rejected questionnaires did not comprise useful answers on this specific question) confirmed the thesis that avatars can affect the player’s engagement and game enjoyment. Inspired by existing studies and our findings we wanted to integrate the concept of an avatar into a simulation game for post graduate engineering students in order to increase their motivation and engagement while playing the game. However, the results indicate no significant difference between the intrinsic motivation and social presence between the game without avatar and the new version with avatar.

However, since only the concept of avatar was evaluated, i.e. no real implementation, the results needs to be verified in a second test based on real mock-ups, so that the player can create their avatar on their own and perceive some kind of interaction with it, in order to feel connected. This connection then effects their motivation and enjoyment. In addition, it seems necessary to repeat the experiment with different kinds of simulation games in order to get a deeper understanding of the boundaries and limitations.

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